

TECHNOGENIC HAZARDS FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF THE THEORY OF SETS

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ABSTRACT

Infinite set of dangerous objects, real and imaginary, is considered as a set of elements in a linear multidimensional continuous space of dangerous factors. The possibility of dividing this space into regions with different levels of danger is elucidated. The spaces of dangerous factors were constructed in the version of mathematical algorithms of separate normative acts of different countries. The quality of these normative acts is evaluated from the point of view of set theory.

Keywords: the object of the increased danger, simulation, simulation modeling, individual risk, R-function.

Statement of the problem. Industrial safety is considered a top priority at all industrial enterprises worldwide. Hazard assessment and its consideration are carried out differently in different countries. For some industries, the application of regulatory acts from different countries will yield different results. Currently, in Ukraine, the fire and explosion hazard of outdoor premises, buildings and installations is assessed based on the regulatory act DSTU B V.1.1-36-2016 "Definition of categories of premises, buildings and outdoor installations based on explosion, fire and fire hazard" [1], in Belarus TKP 474-2013 Categorization of premises, buildings and outdoor installations based on explosion, fire and fire hazard [2], in Russia SP 12.13130.2009 "Definition of categories of premises, buildings and outdoor installations based on explosion, fire and fire hazard" [3]. In

these regulatory documents, an outdoor installation is called a complex of devices and process equipment located outside buildings, structures and constructions. Articles [4-6] examine the validity of such assessments for a specific outdoor installation and the differences in the results of applying the relevant regulations of Ukraine, Belarus, and Russia. This paper proposes further consideration of the problem using the same industrial facility as an example.

Analysis of the latest research and publications. As noted previously, studies were conducted in [4-6] to investigate the reliability of explosion and fire hazard assessments for outdoor installations. The reliability of assessments was understood as the degree of protection of the algorithm from obtaining an erroneous assessment of the facility's hazard. In [4-6], it was shown that an erroneous assessment of the facility's hazard may arise due to the ambiguity (or uncertainty) in the numerical value of the combustible gas and vapor participation factor. Regulatory documents [1-3] propose determining this factor in a plant laboratory or, alternatively, assuming it equal to a constant. The combustible gas and vapor participation factor is ambiguously defined due to the heterogeneity of the gas coming from wells. Ambiguity in the definition of this factor may affect the explosion hazard assessment of an outdoor installation. A case was studied of the explosion hazard assessment of a facility designed to prepare gas for subsequent transportation to a gas pipeline and to a consumer, to which 6 gas wells were connected. There are publications on the assessment of the impact of uncertainty in other production parameters on the assessment of their hazard.

Statement of the problem and its solution. Industrial premises, buildings and outdoor installations are divided into sets (categories) according to the relevant legislation of Ukraine, Russia and Belarus based on their explosion and fire hazard. The division into categories is achieved through the use of a mathematical algorithm that calculates hazardous factors with maximum permissible threshold values. The initial data in such calculations are physical quantities (the amount of hazardous substance, its properties, state, for example, temperature, etc.). Inaccuracy and a certain level of arbitrariness in determining the initial data are

possible. The mathematical algorithms themselves are evaluative, which also introduces a certain uncertainty. In works [4-6], the limits of this uncertainty in the results of hazard determination were investigated using specific examples. The advantages of using hazard criteria created on the basis of p-functions were demonstrated. On the other hand, the indicated uncertainty in the initial data and the approximate nature of the algorithm can be interpreted as fuzziness of the input data and the computational process. In this case, the currently well-developed theories of fuzzy logic and fuzzy sets can be applied. From a set theory perspective, the categorization algorithm implemented in the relevant regulations (as well as the mathematical algorithms of similar regulations) divides objects into sets with varying hazard characteristics and degrees. Let's consider the categorization algorithms [1-3]. Using the mathematical algorithm of this document, premises, buildings, and outdoor installations are divided according to their explosion and fire hazard into categories A, B, C, D, and D. The categories represent disjoint sets. The non-intersection property is artificially embedded in the algorithms of the regulations. For example, in the normative act of Ukraine, DSTU B V.1.1-36:2016 "Definition of categories of premises, buildings and outdoor installations according to explosion and fire hazard," paragraph 6.1 states: "Categories of premises for explosion and fire hazard and fire safety shall be determined by checking the integrity of premises to categories from the largest explosion and fire safety category A to the smallest fire safety category D..." That is, if, in accordance with the mathematical algorithm of the normative act, an object belongs to several categories, then it must be assigned to the category whose letter is closer to the beginning of the alphabet. This is done in normative acts [1-3] and many similar ones. As a result, there will be a subset of objects for which $A \subset B \subset B$, or even $A \cap B \subset B$.

It makes sense to study methods for dividing objects into such sets. Such a study can be conducted for real objects. Consideration of real objects is difficult due to both the availability and reliability of data about them. Also, in the case of real objects, general theoretical safety issues and questions of general forecasts are

excluded from consideration. Next, we will consider a method for representing hazardous production facilities (facilities) in a continuous space of hazardous factors. If any point in the space does not correspond to an existing production facility (facility), we will call this facility an imaginary facility.

According to many regulations, the hazard of objects is determined using the concept of a threshold value. Exceeding the threshold value indicates the hazard of the object. Previous studies have examined the effect of initial data inaccuracy on determining the hazard of objects using threshold values. The use of p-functions [7] in these studies [4-6] has proven successful. If we transform the p-functions so that their values lie between zero and one, we arrive at something resembling fuzzy logic. Using the ideology of fuzzy logic, we adopt the "more dangerous - less dangerous" paradigm, that is, consider an object in terms of its complete or partial danger. However, the p-functions themselves provide us with an entirely different paradigm. With negative values, the object is considered safe. With positive values, various degrees of danger arise (such as not very dangerous, more dangerous, very dangerous, very, very dangerous). The degree of danger varies from zero to infinity. Thus, in regulatory acts that determine the explosion hazard of a room, the hazard is assessed based on the excess explosion pressure. Excess explosion pressure is considered dangerous if its value exceeds 5 kPa. In works [4-6], the value $P-5$ was adopted as a criterion, where P is the value of excess pressure in kilopascals (kPa). In this case, according to the criterion, an object is considered hazardous if the criterion value is greater than 0; if it is less than 0, it is considered safe. Thus, we arrive at a hazard gradation. At 10 kPa, an object is considered hazardous; at 100 kPa, it is considered very hazardous. An excess pressure of 500 kPa would be considered an even greater hazard, and so on.

Difference between objects. Objects differ only in the presence and magnitude of a hazardous factor. The absence of a hazardous factor can be interpreted as the numerical value of this factor being zero. Thus, different objects will correspond to different points in the factor space. Any modification of an object will correspond to a change in its position in the factor space, and therefore,

formally, to a different object. Since it is obvious that any object corresponds to a certain hazard level and a unique point in space, which, in turn, corresponds to a single object, a hazard field will exist in the space of hazardous factors. By hazard, in this case, we mean any numerical hazard criterion derived from certain considerations. In a multidimensional space of hazardous factors, these hazard criteria will form level surfaces. Thus, in a multidimensional space of hazardous factors, it will be possible to distinguish hazardous and safe regions. This can be interpreted as the location of hazardous and safe sets of objects. A hazard criterion can be understood as the threshold value of a hazardous factor, or a somehow formed objective function. Obviously, objective functions can be formed in various ways. Objective functions can be scalar and vector. Several hazard criteria can be considered simultaneously and viewed as a vector. Thus, we can arrive at the concept of a vector space of hazard criteria with elements that are functions of the vectors of the hazard factor space. Thus, the hazard factor space is the space in which hazardous objects are located. Each point corresponds to an individual hazardous object. Real objects will be individual points in this space. The classification of all possible hazardous objects will geometrically correspond to the partition of the factor space into regions. Thus, document [1] will correspond to a partition of the hazard factor space into regions corresponding to categories A, B, C, D, and E. Let us introduce the concepts of simple categories A^n , B^n , B^n . A simple category is a category that corresponds to the implementation of the mathematical algorithm embedded in it, disregarding the impossibility of an object belonging to several categories simultaneously. The sets of categories A, B, C, D, and D (we will denote the sets by the same letters) will be obtained from the sets of simple categories using set operations. So the set of categories $B = B^n - (A^n \cap B^n)$, $B = B^n - A^n$.

Let us consider this approach using the example from [2]. These works studied mathematical algorithms for outdoor installations. Specifically, the influence of the geographical location (climatic conditions) on the reliability of fire hazard assessments for outdoor installations was studied. The reliability of fire

hazard assessments is difficult to determine unambiguously due to the approximate nature of all initial data and the evaluative nature of the algorithm itself. One of the signs of reliability is the coincidence of the results of alternative algorithms (in the case of this work, algorithms from different countries). To determine the criteria for an installation to belong to a particular fire hazard category, a system of criteria based on p-functions [7] was used, similar to [4-6]. The hazard of an outdoor installation was assessed for a specific accident scenario. According to [2, 3], an installation will belong to category "B" if the probability of human death (R) is greater than one in a million.

Thus, the corresponding function will have the form $R^R = R \cdot 10^{-6}$. The criterion associated with the radiation intensity will look like $I^R = I - I_0$ (I_0 is a threshold value equal to 4 kW m^{-2}). Criteria are dimensionless quantities. They must be normalized either to a unit with the appropriate dimension (1 kW m^{-2}), or to a characteristic number (maximum, minimum, average, characteristic, arbitrary, etc.) with the same dimension. The resulting values should be dimensionless.

Dimensionless criteria:

1. $R^R = R \cdot 10^{-6}$
2. $I^R = (I - 4) / (1 \text{ kW m}^{-2})$.

Criteria standardized for the characteristic number (the minimum value at which the installation is considered fire hazardous):

1. $R^R = (R \cdot 10^{-6}) / 10^{-6}$
2. $I^R = (I - 4) / 4 \text{ (kW m}^{-2}\text{)}$.

Let's call these criteria decisive. Their meaning indicates that the explosion hazard determination results for documents [1-3] may differ. Using the decisive criteria, we construct functions that are positive when the answer to the hazard question is positive and negative when the answer to the hazard question is negative. These functions are marked with the superscript R .

Then, the fire hazard criterion for outdoor installations for the Ukrainian document will be a positive value of the function:

$$A^{uk} = I^R, \quad (1)$$

for a Russian document:

$$A^{ru} = R^R, \quad (2)$$

for a Belarusian document:

$$A^{Bel} = R^R + I^R + \sqrt{(R^R)^2 + (I^R)^2} = A^{uk} + A^{ru} + \sqrt{(A^{uk})^2 + (A^{ru})^2}, \quad (3)$$

Next, R-functions from the R1 system [7] are used. Using this technology, criteria for comparing the results of the specified regulations can be created in a simple, straightforward manner. For example, a criterion for matching the results of applying regulations in different countries can be created. Let's create criteria that demonstrate the match between the fire hazard assessment results of:

Ukraine and Belarus:

$$A^{uk-bel} = A^{uk} \cdot A^{bel}, \quad (4)$$

Ukraine and Russia:

$$A^{uk-ru} = A^{uk} \cdot A^{ru}. \quad (5)$$

The criterion for the coincidence of the results of applying the algorithms from [1 - 3] is denoted by $A^{uk-bel-ru}$.

$$A^{uk-bel-ru} = A^{uk-bel} + A^{uk-ru} + \sqrt{(A^{uk-bel})^2 + (A^{uk-ru})^2}. \quad (6)$$

Let us consider the application of this methodology in order to determine the dependence of fire hazard assessments on such a climatic factor as characteristic air temperature, and how the algorithms used in different countries react to this factor. The normative act [2] provides an example of calculating the fire hazard assessment of an outdoor technological installation.

Let us conduct a study for this example. The outdoor installation contains a tank with acetone $V_a = 800 \text{ l} = 0,8 \text{ m}^3$. The molar mass of acetone is $M = 58,08 \text{ kg kmol}^{-1}$. Constants of the Antoine equation: $A = 6.37551$; $B = 1281.721$; $C_a = 237.088$. The chemical formula of acetone is $\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O}$. The density of acetone (liquid) $\rho_l = 790,8 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. The flash point of acetone $t_{fp} = -18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The absolute air temperature in the area of the city of Mogilev is taken as the calculated temperature according to [2] $t_p = 36^\circ\text{C}$.

We will examine how the fire hazard of a storage tank will change with changes in its location (climate). The average (characteristic, or calculated in document [2]) temperature depends on the location. In the hazard determination algorithm, the calculated temperature determines the mass of the reacting substance (m), the reduced mass of the substance (m_{rm}), and the vapor density of the reacting substance (ρ). The results calculated using algorithms [1-3] are shown below.

For the Belarusian document, the surface separating the set of hazardous conditions of the facility from the safe ones is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The interface between a set of hazardous and safe states of an object, according to the hazard criterion of the regulatory act [2] A^{bel} , in coordinates V –

the volume of flammable substance (m^3), T – the estimated temperature ($^{\circ}\text{K}$), and F – the spill area of one liter of flammable liquid (acetone).

The same interface for a Russian document would look like Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The interface between the set of hazardous and safe states of an object according to the hazard criterion for document [3] A^{rus} in coordinates V - the volume of flammable substance (m^3), T - the temperature ($^{\circ}\text{K}$), and F - the spill area of one liter of flammable liquid (acetone).

For the Ukrainian regulatory act [1], Fig. 3

Fig. 3. Dividing surface between a set of hazardous and safe states of an object according to the hazard criterion for regulatory acts [1] A^{ukr} in coordinates V – volume of flammable substance (m^3), T – temperature ($^{\circ}K$), and F – spill area of one liter of flammable liquid (acetone).

These figures show surfaces separating infinite sets of safe states of an object from its hazardous states in the space of hazardous factors (volume of flammable substance, temperature, and spill area of one liter of flammable liquid). To understand the difference in these dividing surfaces, we will plot them on a single graph (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. The dividing surface of a set of hazardous states of an object from safe ones according to the hazard criteria for regulatory acts [1-3] in coordinates V - the volume of flammable substance (m^3), T - temperature ($^{\circ}\text{K}$) and F - the spill area of one liter of flammable liquid (acetone).

The differences in the surface arrangement are clearly visible. This difference demonstrates the degree of approximation of the algorithms for determining the hazards of a given type of production.

With respect to these algorithms, the enterprises differ only in the sets of hazards and their quantitative characteristics. It follows that the graphs above can be viewed not only as surfaces in the state space or implementations of the same production with different quantitative characteristics of hazards, but also as surfaces of different productions with the same types of hazards. This is a consequence of the fact that the nature of production is not specified in the regulatory act.

Conclusions. Industries with the same set of hazards can be considered as a set of points in the space of these factors. In other words, they can be represented by vectors with dimensions equal to the number of hazards, and the numerical values of the coordinates equal to the numerical values of these factors.

The limitation of requiring identical sets of hazards for industries to analyze them in a single space can easily be overcome by supplementing those industries with missing factors that do not have all the factors present in at least one other industry in the set under consideration, with values equal to zero.

There is a significant ambiguity in the algorithmic support of regulatory acts.

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